

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B254
Date: 09 January 2007
Take Off: 10:41:25
Landing: 15:02:56
Flight Time: 4h 21m 31s

Campaign: WINTEX – Instrument Cals

Operating Area: North Sea

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Simon Osborne	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry / CCM2	Ruth Purvis	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
8	Mission Scientist 2	Chawn Harlow	Met Office
9	SWS 1	Ian Rule	Met Office
10	SWS 2	Stuart Rogers	Met Office
11	ARIES	Alan Vance	Met Office
12	MARSS/DEIMOS 1	Dave Pollard	Met Office
13	MARSS/DEIMOS 2	Jeff Brown	Met Office
14	Obs	Philip Gill	Met Office
15	TAFTS	Neil Humpage	Imperial College
16			
17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B254 Track 09-JAN-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b254
 Date: 09JAN07
 Project: WINTEX instrument cals
 Location: north sea

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
100056		3025	0.70 kft	129	pump on
100347		inu	0.70 kft	129	to navigate
100424		drs	0.70 kft	129	running
102550		!	0.70 kft	129	ground power unit failed
102620		!	0.69 kft	129	science power restarted
104125		T/O	0.68 kft	212	cranfield
104334		twc	4.4 kft	018	status good
104527		ASP	5.0 kft	332	open
105253		twc	14.0 kft	342	status 4095
110258		drs	14.0 kft	322	running
110327		bbr	14.0 kft	322	retract
110355		Heiman	14.0 kft	321	zero
110524		JW	14.0 kft	320	zero
111232		WR	14.0 kft	321	weather radar recording
111611		Video	14.0 kft	344	#1 up #2 down
111804	113426	Profile 1	14.0 - 0.86 kft	341	100ft
112544		bbr	6.4 kft	009	extend
112746		rod	4.4 kft	007	now 500ft/min
113105		qnh	2.7 kft	008	998
113537		bbr	1.2 kft	112	retract
113600		heiman	1.2 kft	139	cal07
113701	114702	Run 1.1	0.86 - 0.82 kft	140	100ft
114723		heiman	1.1 kft	169	cal07
114928	115930	Run 1.2	0.81 - 0.89 kft	328	100ft
120106	123500	Profile 2	0.86 - 30.0 kft	180	
120314		bbr	2.0 kft	179	extend
120614		roa	3.5 kft	176	500ft/min to 4000ft then 1000ft/min
121709		P2	15.0 kft	177	interrupted
121904		P2	15.0 kft	352	resumed
122008		Video	16.2 kft	358	#2 to rfc
123008		P2	27.1 kft	358	change to 500ft/min
123522	124023	Run 2.1	30.0 kft	006	downsun box
123829		bbr	30.0 kft	007	retract
123940		TW	30.0 kft	006	status flashing
124142	124645	Run 2.2	30.0 kft	280	cross sun
124755	125258	Run 2.3	30.0 kft	195	into sun
124914		video	30.0 kft	191	#3 up #4 aft
125418	125918	Run 2.4	30.0 kft	109	cross sun
130722	130928	Orbit 1	30.1 - 30.0 kft	253	260M pwd
131044	131242	Orbit 2	30.0 - 29.9 kft	240	240M pwd
131534	131740	Orbit 3	30.2 - 30.1 kft	282	300M swd
132005	132209	Orbit 4	30.1 kft	297	310M swd
132233		!	30.0 kft	305	end science
144954		ASP	7.9 kft	198	closed
150256		Land	0.63 kft	210	Cranfield

B254 Track 09-JAN-07

FAAM Sortie Brief - Back Up Option

Radiation instrument test flight + CAESAR

Flight No: B254

Date: 9th Jan 2007

Aims:

Test Flight:

To carry out an instrument test flight, in particular for ARIES, SWS, MARSS, DEIMOS.

CAESAR part:

The aim of this sortie is to determine the radiative properties of frontal cirrus using multiple frequencies from the range of remote sensing instruments on the aircraft. For closure it is also important to determine the in-situ properties of the cloud and to make radiative measurements of the atmosphere above and below the cirrus. To obtain in-situ vertical distributions perform profile ascents and descents. Measurements should be made **advecting** with the wind, such that the same airmass is continuously measured.

Straight and level runs should be made below, above and in the cirrus. A 100ft run over the sea will be required to measure the SST. Orbits are to be made below the cloud with SWS viewing upwards to determine the phase function of the ice particles.

AQUA Satellite Overpass: **12:38**

Weather conditions:

Test flight:

Stable conditions, clear of high level cloud.

CAESAR part:

Frontal cirrus. Clear sky below the cirrus in the measurement area is essential. Ideally the cirrus should not extend above 35,000ft.

Location:

North Sea

Clearances:

CAESAR part:

NOTAMS will be required for dropping sondes and runs at 100ft.

Instruments required for CAESAR:

Critical: ARIES, SWS, SID1, 2DC, Temp, Humidity, AVAPS

Desirable: MARSS, TAFTS, SHIMS, CPI, SID2, FFSSP, 2DP, CIPs, Heimann, Core chem (auto mode OK)

B254: Radiation instrument test flight + CAESAR

		Manoeuvre	Duration (min)	Sortie part
1	1030Z	Take off & transit to operating area arriving at max alt	50	
2	1120Z	Perform two reciprocal 10 min SLRs at max altitude, clear skies above	25	test
3	1145Z	transit to upwind of cirrus operating area at FL 1000ft below expected cloud base	20	CAESAR
4	1205Z	Fly 1 straight and level run 1000ft below cirrus, orientated across wind, of 10 min. (Note: For non-extensive cirrus, extend all subsequent runs into clear sky a for a short period if necessary then cut run short)	10	CAESAR
5	1215Z	Fly reciprocal run, including two orbits below cloud at SZA (or max) banking angle	15	CAESAR
6	1230Z	Profile ascent to 1000ft above cirrus base	5	CAESAR
7	1235Z	Fly one straight and level run in cloud, orientated across wind, of 10 mins	10	CAESAR
	1238Z	Satellite overpass		
8	1245Z	Profile ascent in cloud to 1000ft below cirrus top	10	CAESAR
9	1255Z	Fly one straight and level run in cloud, orientated across wind, of 10 mins	10	CAESAR
10	1305Z	Profile ascent to 1000ft above cirrus top	5	CAESAR
11	1310Z	Fly three straight and level reciprocal runs 1000ft above cirrus, orientated across wind, each of 10 mins. Drop 1 or 2 sondes during one run, ideally during satellite overpass	35	CAESAR
12	1345Z	Profile descent to 50ft, interrupting as necessary to remain in same airmass	45	test/ CAESAR
13	1430Z	Perform two reciprocal 10 min SLRs at 100ft	25	test/ CAESAR
13	1455Z	Perform profile ascent to convenient transit altitude at 500ft/min within the boundary layer and at 1000ft/min above the boundary layer	20	test
14	1515Z	Transit back to Cranfield	40	
15	1545Z	Land	total:	315mins

Instrument operator instructions:

ARIES and SWS

- Both instruments must point in the same direction as each other (except during cal). ARIES needs to tell SWS where it is pointing.
- Majority of time should be towards the cloud (or sea at 100ft)
- However, still need some data pointing away to characterise the atmosphere above and below the cloud (e.g. ~2 mins of 10 min run)
- For orbits both instruments should view towards cloud for whole time

ARIES

- If it is still unstable for zenith views (shutter open) at high altitudes, it is better to get 30 secs of good data in a 10 min run (with rest of time with shutter closed viewing calcs or nadir) than all bad data – let SWS know which viewing direction and when.

SWS

- Zenith = 6 deg forward

AQUA Satellite overpass:

AQUA 2007/01/09 AQUA ORBITAL PREDICT PLOT EPOCH DATE: 07/01/03
■ lat: 51.57 slon: 358.69 AIRS swath angle: 47.3 deg res: 9 km

Weather conditions

Cold front heading across country, front orientated SW→ NE, heading SW'wards. Cranfield in warm sector, ahead of front at take-off time. Operating region (northern North Sea) in low cloud with some cirrus associated with the back edge of the cold front. Large pressure gradient across country, strong winds 50-60 kts common at surface.

Summary of the flight

A successful flight was carried out as an instrument test flight, primarily for the large radiometers that have recently been re-fitted: MARSS/DEIMOS, SWS, ARIES. A profile was carried out from FL140 (transit altitude) to 100ft over the sea. 50ft was not achievable due to a rough sea, so 100ft was the minimum safely altitude. Some small cumulus were below us during the profile. Thereafter, two 10 min runs were performed across-wind. Aerosol concs were low (100-150/cc). The marine boundary layer was clear of cloud during these runs, but was clearly distinguishable to the naked eye due to its turbidity (sea-salt production?). A profile ascent was then made to max altitude (FL300). During the profile interrupt at FL150 it was noticed that we were contrailing in a moist layer. At FL300 a box pattern was performed, 5 min runs, outside turns, orientated down-, across-, into- and across-sun. This box will act as a reasonable calibration for SWS, SHIMS and MARSS. Unfortunately the second half of the final run (R2.4) went underneath cirrus, so this part will have to be scrapped. We then flew away from the cirrus so as to carry out four orbits (for the SWS) which were clear of any cloud above. The bank angle was ~45deg and the solar zenith angle was ~80deg, so there will be a limited but still useful range of the scattering angles to compare to modelled radiances.

Instrumentation

- (1) DEIMOS- when this is switched on, there is obvious electrical interference on the PCASP and FFSSP. When switched off, the PCASP and FFSSP are fine. This is likely to be a cabling problem. Probable solution- new cables need to be manufactured.
- (2) Nephelometer- strange scattering coefficients, 700nm scatter > 550nm scatter > 450nm scatter throughout the flight (whether in clean MBL or high level). This is not a simple zeroing issue.
- (3) SWS, SHIMS, ARIES, MARSS performed well. New SWS motorised scan head: unstable at times. Not trustworthy yet.
- (4) CO: no decent data. Could not get a calibration.
- (5) TAFTS: noisy detectors throughout flight.

Note- there was a sudden power drop-out from the GPU during at engine start-up. This MAY account for some of the instrument problems (CO, neph ?).

Mission Scientist's Log

S. P. OSBORNE

Flight No **B.254**.....

Date **07/01/07**.....

Page **1** of **2**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					T/O Cranfield
					thro' Sea 2/8. Some 20- droplets.
	DEIMOS				INTERFERING WITH PCASP + FTSSP → heavy clear skies above → NO Ci noise.
~11000	R	FL140		TRANSIT	
~1103		FL140			Some light cloud ahead + to left.
~1110+		FL140			pan's thro' some red. level cloud. v. uneven.
~111430		FL140			seem to be clear of Ci above → some cloud now above - hard to tell height over coast (Teeside area)
111801	P1 ↓	FL140 ↓	341	54° 42' N 0° 54' W	Start profile descent. broken Cu below - 2/8
112728	P1 ↓	3500'			change to 500ft/min some Ci also clear of Cu now!!
112926	P1 ↓	2500' ↓			Turbid - visibility red. Good vert signal.
113426	P1 →	100'	013	55° 51' N 0° 24' W	End profile descent. Signal. squalls 6-7. winds 24/228' wts
113659	R1.1	100'	140	55° 54' N 0° 12' W	Start SLR low-level. PCASP 125ft. 80% / sec cu FTSSP
114700	R1.1	100'	145	55° 24' N 0° 30' W	End Run. 24/240° winds
114928	R1.2	100'	278	55° 30' N 0° 24' W	Start reciprocal SLR low-level
115928	R1.2	100'	377	56° 00' N 0° 00' W	End Run. Good low-level bit!!
120105	P2 ↑	100' ↑	180	56° 00' N 0° 00' W	Start profile ascent.
120703	P2 ↑	4000' ↑			1000ft/min
~120945	P2 ↑	6000' ↑			kept close to zero now.

can see top of haze + sea to front/right
see salt → large particles → low level

Mission Scientist's Log S.R. OSBORNE

Flight No **B...254**.....

Date 09/01/07.....

Page 2 of 2

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
121709	R2->	FL150	?	55°0'030"E	Attempt climb. Ci all over
	R2->	FL150			CONTRAILING. (in turn) corner. record near-fach
122954	R2->	FL270	359	55°06'N 0°54'E	500 ft/min
123459	R2->	FL300	358	56°036' 1°12'	End profile ascent. Ci clearing
128523	R2.1	FL300	007		Start BOX PATTERN. leg 1. Down-sun clear above - phew!
124071	R2.1	FL300	005	57°12'N 1°02'E	End Run.
124140	R2.2	FL300	280	57°18' 1°04'	Start Run } ACROSS SUN.
124645	R2.2	FL300	277	57°24' 1°06'	End Run }
124750	R2.3	FL300	195	57°18' 1°06'	Start Run } INTO SUN.
125553	R2.3	FL300	191	57°01' 1°12'	End Run }
125415	R2.4	FL300	109	56°54'N 1°30'E	Start Run } ACROSS SUN.
125915	R2.4	FL300	10	56°48' 2°36'	End Run. } some Ci tonight.
					start pass under jet, sun sits at end of run
130720	01↓	FL300	260	57°23' 2°12'	Start orbit } clear skies above.
130925	01↓	FL300	260	57°30' 2°30'	End orbit } <u>O_{sun} = 80°</u>
131043	02↓	FL300	240	57°30' 2°24'	Start orbit
131240	02↓	FL300	240	57°30' 2°30'	End orbit. Return for SWS. (viewing to within -6°)
131533	03↓	FL300	300		Start orbit Return.
131738	03↓	FL300	300	57°30'N 2°18'E	End orbit. clear skies above
132004	04↓	FL300	310	57°44'N 2°06'E	Start orbit Return dr. on below EWS
132206	04↓	FL300	310	57°42' 2°12'	End orbit. O _{sun} = 81.2° (plenty of Ci under 2000)
(Groun) ORBITS →					END SCIENCE!

45° bank angle.

0 → 20

(Q+10) → 10 → (20+10)
(A-20) → 2 → (10-20)

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG FOR FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight Number : B254

Date : 9/1/07

Operator and contact info :Ruth Purvis(rupu@faam.ac.uk)

Problems with Instruments

CO	Problem after power dropout on power changeover U/S for whole of flight
O₃	None
NO_x	None
SO₂	Not operated
TDLAS	None
WAS	Not operated

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B254

Date: 9/01/07	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 07:35:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 1
---------------	---------------	--------------------	---------------	---------------	---------------	---------------	---------------	-------------

G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
11:00:00																Deimos noise effecting PCASP and FFSSP	
11:18:11	Noise		Off	1	1											Start Profile 1 from FL140	
11:19:20	Noise		Off	1	1											FL130	
11:20:01	Noise		Off	1	1											FL120	
11:21:02	Noise		Off													FL110	
11:22:09	Noise		Off													FL100	
11:23:10	Noise		Off	1												FL090	
11:24:09	Noise		Off													FL080	
11:25:02	12	0.09	0	3	2											FL070	
11:26:11	15	0.10		10	1											FL060	
11:27:02	55	0.09		10	1											FL050	
11:28:25	70	0.10		10	1											FL040	
11:30:19	85	0.10		15	3											FL030	
11:32:23	100	0.10	1	15	3											FL020	
11:33:56	125	0.10	2	30	5											FL010	
11:34:25	130	0.10		30	5											End of Profile 1 @ 100'	
11:36:59																Start Run 1.1 @ 100'	
11:38:00	125	0.11	7	30	5												
11:40:00	110	0.11	11	30	8												
11:42:00	110	0.11		40	5												
11:44:00	100	0.10	12	40	3												
11:47:00																End of Run 1.1	
11:49:27																Start Run 1.2 @ 100'	
11:50:00	110	0.10	14	30	1												
11:52:00	130	0.10	15	25	5												
11:54:00	140	0.10	16	30	5												
11:56:00	115	0.11	17	30	5												
11:58:00	125	0.10	18	30	5												
11:59:28																End of Run 1.2	
12:01:05	200	0.09	19	30	5											Start Profile 2 from 100'	
12:01:33	125	0.10		30	5											FL010	
12:03:16	100	0.10		15	1											FL020	
12:05:06	90	0.09	20	15	1											FL030	
12:07:04	60	0.09		10	1											FL040	
12:08:14	35	0.10		10	1											FL050	
12:09:11	15	0.12		2	1											FL060	
12:10:10	10	0.11		2	1											FL070	
12:11:09	5	0.08		1												FL080	
12:11:59	5	0.08		1	1											FL090	
12:12:56	3	0.08	21	1	1											FL100	
12:13:54	8	0.09														FL110	
12:14:49	6	0.08														FL120	
12:15:30	Noise		Off													FL130	
12:16:14	Noise		Off													FL140	
12:17:09	Noise		Off	1												FL150	
12:19:55	Noise		Off	1												FL160	

SWS and SHIMS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight # **B254** Date **09/JAN/2007** Operat or(s) **S. Rogers / I. Ruzic** log page **1** of **3**

Note to operator: Indicate whether entry refers to SWS or SHIMS
SWS only used for R2-1 until 04

Time	Run id	Alt/FL	MIRR Pos	Int Times		Remarks	S W S	U S H	L S H
				Vis	NIR				

10:41	TAKEOFF								
10:42:10		↑	DARK	200	—	Then scene		✓	
10:47:45		↑	DARK	250	—	— " —			✓
						FL102 @ 10:49			
						T = 14°C			
10:56:24	Transit	~FL140	DARK	350		Then scene			✓
11:04:22			DARK	250		Then scene (over bright cloud?)			✓
11:08:35			DARK	200		Then scene		✓	
11:09						In cloud briefly			
						T = 16°C			
11:14			DARK	350		Then scene			✓
11:18:04	P1 ↓	1							
11:27:14		~3500ft	DARK	500		Then scene			✓
11:28:15			DARK	200				✓	
11:37:01	R1-1	100ft							
11:47:10	end of run		DARK	200		Then scene		✓	
11:49:15			DARK	500		— " —			✓
						T = 12			
11:49	R1-2								
11:59	end of run								
12:01	P2 ↑					500ft/m until 3500ft. Hazy			
12:12:04			DARK	200		Then scene		✓	
12:12:20			DARK	500		Then scene			✓
12:35	R2-1	FL300	DARK	400		Then scene		✓	
12:35		"	6F	"		Clear above & below.		✓	
12:41	R2-2	"				Across sun			
12:47:57	R2-3	"				Into sun			
12:54	R2-4	"				Across sun			
12:59			DARK	100		Then scene		✓	
"			DARK	200		— " —			✓
13:05			DARK	400		— " —		✓	
13:07	O1 L	260							
			DARK	150		Then scene			✓
13:16:47	O2 L								
13:15	O3 R								
13:20	O4 R								
13:26			DARK	100		Then scene		✓	
"			DARK	150		"			✓
14:04			DARK	100				✓	
"			DARK	150					✓
14:05			DARK	250				✓	
"			DARK	350					✓

ARIES flight log

Flight: *B254* page 1 of 2

Date: *9-1-7* Operator(s): *VANCE* Res: *1* Gain A: *2* B: *2*

Loc./Notes: *First flight after upgrade - N. SEA*

Scans: either "[IGMs][co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
0818	on pan.	ARIES	on				1st attempt to correct failed, 2nd OK
082435	"	1x60	C	C	22.6	32.4	
082523	"	"	H	C	22.2	34.9	
090035	"	"	C	C	71	31	changed view in middle
090118	"	"	C	C	71	30.8	views displayed with these cal. diff show different θ_T on detectors
090154	"	"	H	C	71	31	
090704	"	30x1	Z	O	71	31	
090737	"	30x1	N	O	71	31	
090841	"	"	NSS	O	71	31	
091135	"	1x60	C	C	71	31	
091209	"	"	H	C	71	31	
091305	"	091336	Z	O	71	32	60 Coadds of 60 - cogs
091412	"	091526	Z	O	71	31	
091608	"	1x60	C	O	71	31	
091712	"	1x60	H	O	71	31	
1015.	ambient air temp = 287 (mean) 285, aries ~ 280 in long \sim CO ₂						
1021	GPU fail & all science power out.						
1029.	Trouble restarting ARIES. Laptop rebooted						
1032	HURRAH						
1040	ish T/O						
104725	"	1x60	C	C	50.9	30.5	Recorded to Garfield_0701...
104817	transit	1x60	C	C	65	31	
104937	"	1x60	C	C	71	31	
105014	"	1x60	C	H	71	31	
105712	"	"	C	C	71	31	
105746	"	"	C	H	71	31	
105830	"	105949	C/O	Z	71	31	
110019	"	1x60	C/O	C	71	31	
110055	"	1x60	C	H	71	31	HShroud 67° → 71 at end.
110142	"	1x60	C	C	71	31	
110219	"	"	C	H	71	31	

sometimes

44

ARIES flight log

Flight: B254

page 2 of 2

Date: 9-1-7

Operator(s): VANCE

Res: 1

Gain A:2 B:2

Loc./Notes: *First post-upgrade test flight*

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
110343	trans.	0608	Z	0	71	31	using last cal. - looks bad
110529	"	1x60	C	C	70	31	
110633	"	"	H	C	71	31	Real line ^Z spectra all look poor
110720	"	110857	Z	0	70	30	n ₂ better
111030 110857							
111133	"	1x60	C	0	71	30	
	R)						second LL @ H Cal. Shtr 0.
<p>At this point we started low level runs. Knowing what happens to my guts was at 100' in 55 kts wind & stopped scribbling. My guts did not really recover after that & hence this log has not restarted. All items listed here are included in the house keeping data in the IGM files & ASCII HSK files (although these may be corrupt) except the shutter position. PLEASE pay careful attention to the target temperatures including (especially?) the shrouds as these may wander when the shutter is open, as it was for most of the unlogged measurements.</p> <p>I apologise for the state of this log.</p>							

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	09/01/07	Flight	B254	log pages
Operator(s)	Pollard/Brown		Campaign	WINTEX		
Departure	Cranfield		Arrival	Cranfield		

**System start
MARSS**

Visual pod inspection						X
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						X
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						X
FERA on			at time	08:16		
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	22°C	Ch	23°C	Ch18	20°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on			at time	08:16		
Initial target temperatures	Hot	289	Cold	289		
Target heating						X
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						X
Scanning on (LMD box)			at time	08:20:10		
Scan indication		Monitor)		Visual	X

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers						X
Turn on Deimos CPU						X
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						X
Start Deimos Software			at time	09:14:30		
Initial target temperatures	Hot	288	Cold	288		
Target heating						X
Scan indication		Monitor)		Visual	
Weather	Cloud		Precip			
	Surface		Pressure			
	Other					

System functionality check (after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC} = t_{DRS} +$		at time		
Brightness temps 'sensible'					
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot		Cold	
	Deimos:	Hot		Cold	
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B	
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)	
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)

Power changeover

Headset on before start		
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.	
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)		
Exit Deimos Software (x)		
POWER CHANGEOVER		
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton	
Restart Deimos Software		
System running again		at time

Flight:

B254

KEY

- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- OK
- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nevezorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turbulence Check Press:
- Turbulence Diff Press:
- Weather Radar:

DLUs:

- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:

Aerosol

- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3010A:
- INC:
- VACC:

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

Report Created 19/01/2007 11:32:15

Last Updated:

09/01/2007 16:19:24

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B254

Date: 9th January 2007

Instruments

1. Cruciform GPS – u/s
2. TWC now operational
3. 2D-C u/s
4. Can't print from "old" laptops as print driver not compatible with Win '95 USB access.
5. DIEMOS causes noise in PCASP
6. Ground cart power failure at change over caused power dump. Restarted after APU engine start
7. CO would not perform stable calcs after power drop out.
8. Neph degraded by power drop out.

Aircraft

- 1.

Satcom H Calls - Nil

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 09.01.07

Flight No: 8254

Pre-Flighter: MS

<u>Item</u>	<u>✓ or x</u>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	
<u>Aircraft Cabin</u>				
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS	Checked	
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Align	
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	<i>Col Gas reading 5.17 (not 4.25)</i>
17	<input type="checkbox"/> N/A	FWVS	Set up	
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC	ON & Checked	
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked	
23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
24	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hubs x 4	Checked ON	
25	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	& CB on Port Fwd SSP
26	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	
27	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> WLS	CGPS	Set up	
28	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
External Checks overleaf				→

Pre-Flighter's Log

<u>Item</u>	<u>✓ or x</u>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
<u>External</u>				
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	<i>Clr, Red, Clr, Clr (fwd → aft)</i>
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	All other covers	Removed	
40	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
41	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				Signed
43	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		<i>[Signature]</i>
44	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	ICEX applied		<i>[Signature]</i>
45	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Traps empty (weekly only)		<i>[Signature]</i>

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B254:

Log	Reason
Cloud Physics Processing	Awaiting completion of processing

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	19 Jan 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

2 x Upward Facing Cameras

2 x Down/Rearward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

Dr Jonathan P. Taylor

Manager Atmospheric Radiation Research Group
Met Office
Cordouan 2 W079
FitzRoy Road
Devon
EX1 3PB
UK

Tel: +44 (0)1392 884647

Fax: +44 (0)1392 885681

E-mail: jonathan.p.taylor@metoffice.gov.uk